

Morphological Characteristics and Frequency of Duodenal Ulcer in Patients with Metabolic Syndrome in Khorazm Region

**Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich¹, Musaeva Iroda Mansurbekovna²,
Radjapov Adilbek Anvarbekovich³**

¹Assistant Professor of the "Pathomorphology" Department of Urganch branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

²Chief physician of Khorezm Regional Blood Transfusion Center

³Chief physician of the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of Khorezm Region

Annotation: in this article, in the course of scientific work carried out by the researcher and the scientific supervisor, the epidemiology of duodenal ulcer disease in patients with metabolic syndrome in Khorezm region, frequency of occurrence, location of the ulcer, complications with bleeding, statistical analysis, occurrence in relation to gender, district and detection of the disease in the urban area was studied.

Archival documents, macro-preparations, and histo-preparations of the last three years were used in the scientific work of the adult department of the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of Khorezm region.

Relevance of the topic: It was found out that metabolic syndrome, i.e., body weight increase, visceral obesity, occurrence of carbohydrate and fat metabolism in the body, has increased by 21% in the last 10 years. In the USA, this indicator has increased by 34% in the last 5 years, while in European countries it has increased by 20.8%. Metabolic syndrome is observed on average in 56% of people over 40 years old, 44% mainly in people over 50 years old. This, from an economic point of view, leads to premature illness of the working-age population and a high demand for the health department of each country.

In the Russian Federation and the countries of Central Asia, this indicator is 16.8% on average, 51% are over 50 years old, 36% are over 40 years old, 11% are 20-30 years old, and others are 9%. This confirms the relevance of the problem and at the same time makes it necessary to study the morphological changes of the activity of the gastrointestinal tract in patients with this disease. It plays an important role in improving the quality of life of the population. In particular, in our country, metabolic syndrome mainly affects more than 4.2 million women, 38% of whom are of reproductive age. This is very important for the protection of the mother and child, which makes the topic relevant at the moment.

On average, in 2022, 22% of the total funds were allocated for the restoration of reproductive health of women with metabolic syndrome in Uzbekistan, while in 2023, this figure will be 36% and is increasing year by year. In this study, we present information about the occurrence of interrelated clinical morphological changes in metabolic syndrome, such as the enlargement of the duodenum, its size, and the occurrence of gallstone disease.

However, in the literature and scientific research of foreign and CIS countries, there is no information on morphological and immunohistochemical changes of the duodenum in metabolic syndrome, and this, in turn, allows for the development of specific recommendations for medical practice.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, the anamnestic analysis, statistical analysis, epidemiology of patients with metabolic syndrome in the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of the Khorezm region, the frequency of occurrence, the location of the wound, complications with

bleeding, the occurrence in relation to gender, pathological in the 12 duodenum in the district and city The goal is to determine the changes.

The results obtained: within the framework of the conducted scientific research, 12 cases of finger ulcers with metabolic syndrome were identified in the district and city sections of patients with metabolic syndrome. Table 1.

Table 1. Meeting of patients in district and city section.

As can be seen in the above table, 20 out of 12 finger ulcers were found among patients with metabolic disease in the regions and cities. This, in turn, is distinguished by the fact that it is a higher indicator than other districts and cities.

When studying the gender of patients, a higher rate was found in women than in men, that is, 40 men and 60 women. Table 2.

Table 2. Patient encounter by gender.

In the scientific research on the conducted scientific work, it was found that the patients have other comorbidities than the main disease, that is, 3 gastritis, 5 gastric motility disorders, 6 gastroduodenitis, 25 ulcers of the 12 fingers and other diseases.

A 63-year-old female patient went to the medical institution complaining of stomach pain, nausea, severe pain after a while, and during the endoscopy examination, it was found that there was a pathological change in the wall of the duodenum. Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Endoscopic examination of the duodenum.

Figure 1. In the endoscopic examination, a 3.0x5.0 cm size, densely constitutive, well-defined brown ulcer was found in the duodenum.

A 43-year-old female patient was found to have an ulcer in the upper part of the duodenum during endoscopic examination. Fig. 2.

Figure 2. It is a wound measuring 3.5x5.0 cm, pale yellow in color, with unclear borders, and it is distinguished by a slight penetration into the intestinal wall.

In a 58-year-old female patient, 12 fingers penetrated the wall of the intestine 0.3x0.5 cm, the borders of the wound are clearly visible, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Endoscopic view of a duodenal ulcer in a 58-year-old patient.

During research, a 60-year-old female patient was found to have a newly developing ulcer in the antral part of the stomach during endoscopic examination of the duodenum. Figure 4.

Figure 4. The location of the ulcer in the antral part of the stomach.

Most of the patients who applied to the medical institution underwent surgery, and as a result of the operation, the macropreparations sent to the pathologist for anatomical examination were histologically processed and examined.

Figure 5. A micropreparation prepared as a result of histological examination of 12-finger intestinal ulcer disease. Paint G-E. 10x10

Figure 6. Histological appearance of duodenal ulcer disease. Paint G-E. 10x10

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that there is an ulcer in the bulb, antral, body, small curvature, cardiac part of the stomach from the complicated ulcer of duodenal ulcer, which is common in women.

It was found that 12 out of 20 patients with metabolic disease in the region and cities had ulcer disease. This, in turn, was distinguished by the fact that it was a higher indicator than other districts and cities.

When studying the gender of patients, a higher rate was found in women than in men, that is, 40 men and 60 women.

It was found that the patients had other comorbidities than the main disease, that is, 3 cases of gastritis, 5 cases of gastric motility disorders, 6 cases of gastroduodenitis, 25 cases of ulcer disease and other diseases.

Many patients went to the medical institution complaining of stomach pain, nausea, severe pain after a meal, and endoscopy revealed pathological changes in the wall of the duodenum.

REFERENCES:

1. Artikova D. O., Ruzmetova D. T. XORAZM VILOYATIDA HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA SIYDIK YO 'LLARI INFEKSIYASINI KECHISHI VA UNGA OLIB KELUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 3-4.
2. Bekchanov A. J. et al. Causes of death in infants born to women affected by Covid-19 disease //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 34-38.
3. Khasanovich K. R., Tulibaevna R. D., Ziyaevich T. H. DISTRIBUTION OF PERINATAL DISEASE IN NEWBORN CHILDREN IN KHORZAM PROVINCE BY CITY AND DISTRICT AND CAUSES OF DEATH //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2021. – Т. 5. – С. 82-85.
4. Каримов Р., Аvezов М. Оценка перинатальных случаев смерти, уровня и состояния заболеваний уха, горла и носа //Журнал вестник врача. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 60-63.
5. Karimov R. X., Tursunov X. Z., Ruzmetova D. T. Modern approaches to perinatal disease in diabetes in pregnant women //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 173-179.
6. Karimov R. X, & Musaev U. M. (2023). ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH AND COMMISSION FORENSIC EXPERTISES CONDUCTED ON LIVING PERSONS. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*, 1(5), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/423>
7. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рuzметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.
8. Каримов, Р. Х., Мусаев, У. М., Рuzметова, Д. Т., & Султанов, Б. Б. (2023, October). ЯТРОГЕНИЯ В НЕОНАТОЛОГИИ (ПО ДАННЫМ ЛЕТ. ОБЗОР). In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 76-78).
9. Каримов Р. Х. и др. ВРАЧЕБНЫЕ ОШИБКИ В ПРАКТИКЕ АКУШЕРОВ-ГИНЕКОЛОГОВ //Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 114-117.
10. Kh K. R. et al. PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY AIRCRAFT CHANGES IN INFANTS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH COVID-19 //JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 21-28.
11. Матякубова С., Рuzметова Д. Особенности клинического течения при преждевременном излитии околоплодных вод и принципы ведения беременных //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2019. – №. 1 (107). – С. 175-177.

12. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Фоновые факторы, влияющие на течение беременности и её исход при преждевременных разрывах плодных оболочек //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2018. – №. 4 (104). – С. 203-205.
13. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. CLINICAL PRACTICAL ASSESSMENT APPLICATION OF POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION AS A TEST FOR ASSESSING MICROBIOCINOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 1. – С. 37-49.
14. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. OCCURRENCE OF UTERINE MYOMA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KHOREZM REGION //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 489-492.
15. SA M., DT R. RISK FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PRETERM PREMATURE RUPTURE OF FETAL MEMBRANES IN PREGNANT WOMEN //European Science Review. – 2018. – Т. 1.
16. Sabirjanovich Y. B. et al. ETHERIOLOGICAL FACTORS OF DEATH IN PNEUMONIAS FOUND IN NEWBORNS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 1-4.
17. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Бекчанов, А. Ж. (2023, July). COVID-ўтказган оналардан туғилган чақалоқларда пневмония касаллигининг асоратлари. In *Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 10-12).
18. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Джуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). COVID-19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ЛИМФА ТУГУНЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ (ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИ ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯ ЭКСПЕРТИЗА БЮРОСИ, ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТ ПЕРИНАТАЛ МАРКАЗИ). *Молодые ученые, 2*(3), 15-16.
19. Tulibayevna R. D. Characteristics of Urogenital Tract Microbiota During Pregnancy //Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 249-254.
20. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Джуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). ПАНДЕМИЯ ДАВРИДА ПНЕВМОНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИ БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ЛИМФА ТУГУНЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ЎЛИМ САБАБЛАРИ. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 3*(1), 197-201.
21. Юлдашев Б. С., Каримов Р. Х., Бекчанов А. Ж. COVID-19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ПНЕВМОНИЯНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТИ //International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists" Sustainable Development: Problems, Analysis, Prospects"(Poland). – 2023. – С. 26-28.
22. Yuldashev B. S. et al. Causes of Pneumonia In Infants Born of Mothers Infected With Covid-19 //International Journal of Integrative and Modern Medicine. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 9-16.
23. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). OCCURRENCE OF CLINICAL PALATE AND LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3*(11), 80-85.
24. Kuryazov Akbar Quranbaevich, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Ruzmetova Dilfuza Tulibaevna, & Bobojanov Yoldoshboy Bakhtiyor o'g'li. (2024). PREVENTION OF PERIODONTITIS DISEASE IN MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION, 1(1), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10599587>

25. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). A CASE OF LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(9), 547-552.
26. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RATE OF GLAUCOMA IN PENSION AGE CITIZENS (2023 in the example of the city of Urganch). *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(1), 4-7.
27. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RELATIONSHIP OF OTHER TYPES OF DISEASES WITH EYE DISEASES. *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА*, 2(1), 29-35.
28. Юлдашев, Б. С., Исмаилов, О., Каримов, Р. Х., & Исмаилов, О. (2023). Хомила ва янги туғилган чақалоқлар мурдасининг суд тиббий экспертизаси (Текшируви). *Ўқув қўлланма: Т.: “О ‘ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI” NMIU*, 96.
29. Сатликов, Р. К., Юлдашев, Б. С., Закиров, Ш. Ю., Каримов, Р. Х., & ИЗУЧЕНИЯ, М. (2022). ИНФЕКЦИЯХ МОЧЕВЫХ ПУТЕЙ. *Монография:-Т.: “О ‘ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI” NMIU*, 84.
30. Турсунов, Х. З., Каримов, Р. Х., Сапаев, Д. Ш., & Сапаев, М. Ф. (2022). Буйрак ва буйрак усти беши касаллиги, уни даволаш усуллари ҳамда асоратлари (адабиётлар шарҳи).
31. Quranbaevich, K. A., Khasanovich, K. R., & Tulibaevna, R. D. (2024, February). CARIES DISEASE IN YOUNG CHILDREN. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 35-37).
32. Юлдашев, Б. С., Ходжаниязов, А. А., Каримов, Р. Х., & Жуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). ЧАСТОТА МЕТАСТАЗИРУЮЩЕГО РАКА МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ ВОЗРАСТА. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 2(2), 141-143.
33. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., Safarboevich, R. S., & Azamatovich, K. A. (2024). DYNAMICS OF ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ONE-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 2(2), 560-563.
34. Sobirjanevich, Y. B., Alievich, M. A., & Xasanovich, K. R. (2024). Этиология Гепатоцеллюлярной Карциномы: Особое Внимание Жировой Болезни Печени. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 26-36.
35. Рузматов, П. Ю., Матмуротов, К. Ж., Бабаджанов, А. Р., Каримов, Р. Х., & Рузметов, Б. А. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВЫПОЛНЕНИЯ РЕКОНСТРУКТИВНЫХ ВМЕШАТЕЛЬСТВ У БОЛЬНЫХ СИНДРОМОМ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ СТОПЫ. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(3), 96-112.
36. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., Zhumabaevich, K. U., Farkhadovich, A. A., Azamatovich, K. A., ... & Alisherovich, K. D. (2024). PREGNANCY PLANNING FOR WOMEN WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES IN NUKUS CITY (2022-2023). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 233-241.
37. Abdullayev, O. (2024). XORAZM VILOYATIDA GEPATIT S KASALLIGINING TARQALISHI. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(3), 189-196.
38. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Jumabaevich, K. U., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibievna, R. D., Azamatovich, K. A., & Dilshadovich, J. D. (2024). PATHOLOGICAL OCCURRENCE AND COMPLICATIONS OF THE DIABETIC TOPIC SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE

- 2 DIABETES DISEASE WHO APPLY TO THE OUTPATIENT. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 219-227.
39. Matyakubova, S. A., & Ruzmetova, D. T. (2018). Risk factors of development of preterm premature rupture of fetal membranes in pregnant women. *European science review*, (9-10-2), 96-97.
40. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Jumabaevich, K. U., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibievna, R. D., & Raimberganovna, M. F. (2024, March). STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETES 2 DISEASE (in the example of the city of Nukus in 2023). In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 162-165).
41. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., Мадаминов, Ф. А., & Мадаминов, А. С. (2024). СНИЖЕНИЕ ЧАСТОТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ НОЗОКОМИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФЕКЦИИ МОЧЕВОГО ТРАКТА ПРИ СОЧЕТАНИИ АНТИБИОТИКОВ С ИММУНОМОДУЛЯТОРАМИ. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(12), 107-109.